

INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOUR :

The term "information seeking behavior" describes how humans look for and use information. Wilson first used the word in his 1981 study, arguing that the then-current "information needs" were not useful as a foundation for a research program because "need" could not be directly observed, but people's information-seeking behaviors could be watched and studied. Nonetheless, there is a growing body of research in the field of information searching that links behaviors to fundamental requirements.

Searching for information is a fundamental human behavior. It predates the human race. In order to hunt, fish, farm, and defend themselves, early humans sought for information.

Wilson (1999) provided an overview of information seeking and other information behavior models, demonstrating the connection between communication and information behavior in general as well as information searching and seeking in information retrieval systems.

Additionally, it is proposed that different models handle related problems in related ways in both information seeking and information searching research, and that the models are complementary rather than antagonistic. Lastly, a different problem-solving model is offered, which is supposed to serve as a foundation for connecting the models in suitable research approaches.

Searching for Information Behavior can be defined as a person's approach to obtaining and sourcing information for their own usage, knowledge building, and updating. Another crucial activity in the academic setting is information seeking. It is linked to all of the work that faculty members do, including research, teaching, and service.

The phrase "information seeking" frequently acts as a catch-all for a group of connected ideas and problems. The phrase has resonance in the library industry when discussing database administration and design, community information needs, reference services, and many other subjects.

A single, useful definition is still challenging, though.

Psychological aspect of the information seeking behavior

Taylor has examined the demand for information from the perspective of human behavior psychology and has distinguished four stages of information need, which are as follows:

- **Visceral need:-**

A genuine but unspoken informational need

- **Conscious need:-**

a vague decision-making sector.

- **Formal need:-**

a topic of uncertainty that can be articulated in specific terms.

- **Comprised need:-**

A need is translated into what the file and resources can provide.

Models of Information Seeking Behaviour

The majority of information-seeking behavior models are assertions that try to explain an information-seeking behavior, its causes and effects, or the connections between different information-seeking behavior phases. However, they are at a pre-theoretical level, very few models go as far as to identify relationships among theoretical propositions, however they may indicate

relationships that could be useful to investigate or test. However, compared to models focused on information-seeking behavior or information searching, there seem to be fewer models of information behavior. Each model has been examined separately.

Concerns about how people use information in their workplaces are the driving force for research on information-seeking behavior. A perceived need leads to information seeking behavior, whereby the information user places demands on formal or informal information sources or services to meet that need, with varying degrees of success.

Wilson’s Model of Information Behaviour (1981) :

According to Wilson, information-seeking behavior develops as a result of the need that an information user perceives at various points in time. The user requests formal or informal information sources or services to meet that need. Finding pertinent information is either successful or unsuccessful as a result of these information demands. If the outcome is favorable, the person uses the knowledge they have discovered and may completely or partially meet the perceived need.

Fig : Wilson Model Diagram (source- Patel, P. Y., & Oza, N. D. (2021). MODELS OF INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOUR: AN OVERVIEW. In Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR) & Sardar Patel University, *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)* (Vol. 8, Issue 9) [Journal-article]. <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2109116.pdf>).(It is used for purpose of study)

Wilson's Model of Information Behaviour (1996):

Wilson created a new model that is an update to his information behavior model from 1981. Different cycles of information activities take place in this model. Wilson's first model serves as the foundation for his 1996 model.

The essential idea of this updated model is that "information processing and use" becomes a crucial component of the feedback loop depicted at the bottom of the model if information needs are to be met. In order to understand user behavior, the 1996 model also offers four pertinent characteristics for information-seeking behavior. These are stress/coping, risk/reward, social learning theory and 'self-efficacy'.

Wilson therefore incorporated traits from several human behavior models into his own. In this way, the model highlights how information behavior theory is interconnected, regardless of whether it originates from information science research traditions or other fields.

Dervin's Model (1983) :

Dervin's sense-making theory is more than just a description of how people seek information; it has evolved over many years. This theory, according to her, is a collection of presumptions, a theoretical viewpoint, a methodological approach, a collection of research techniques, and a practice intended to deal with information viewed as a human tool for making sense of a world that is thought to be both chaotic and organized. One of the first scholars to develop the sense-making method and adapt it to the requirements of the typical citizen was Dervin. His method for evaluating how people make sense of their surroundings and apply resources to solve problems was based on a set of conceptual premises and associated methodologies.

Four consistent components are used to implement sense making: a situation in time and space that highlights the differences between the desired situation and the contextual situation; an outcome that represents the results of the sense-making process; and a bridge that provides a way to bridge the gap between the situation and the outcome. Situation, Gap/Bridge, and result are the three triangles that Dervin has used to represent these components.

Fig : Dervin's sense making model
(source- Price, Rebecca & Wrigley, Cara & Matthews, Judy. (2017). Design-led innovation and sensemaking: opportunities to connect.)
(It is used for purpose of study)

Ellis Model :

Ellis researched the views and actions of social scientists at the University of Sheffield in the United Kingdom, including psychologists, educators, economists, sociologists, historians, geographers, and political scientists. Based on the findings, Ellis distinguished six main categories—1) beginning, 2) chaining, 3) browsing, 4) discriminating, 5) monitoring, and 6) extracting—that encompass the traits of social scientists' information-seeking behaviors.

- Starting is The method which the user uses to start looking for information. It represents the activities that made up the first search, such as asking certain coworkers.
- Following footnotes, citation chains, or other referential connections between items is known as "chaining."
- Browsing is a type of Searching in a potentially interesting region in a semi-structured or semi-directed manner.
- Differentiating is Applying variations among sources as a filter to the type and caliber of information analyzed.
- Monitoring is Keeping abreast of advancements in an area by keeping an eye on specific sources. It entails staying current.
- Extracting is the process of carefully choosing pertinent information from a source.
- Verifying the conclusion might be characterized as typing up any loose ends using a last search.

The relationship between these traits or elements makes up the behavioral model itself. These may be interested in distinct information-seeking patterns in different ways.

Fig : Ellies Model Diagram (source- Patel, P. Y., & Oza, N. D. (2021). MODELS OF INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOUR: AN OVERVIEW. In Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR) & Sardar Patel University, *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)* (Vol. 8, Issue 9) [Journal-article]. <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2109116.pdf>).(It is used for purpose of study)

Sandstrom's Optimal Foraging Theory (1994) :

According to Sandstrom (1994), "information foraging" refers to the actions involved in identifying, locating, and managing information sources in a networked context. The basic principle behind this theory is that people are driven primarily by their own self-interest, or individualism. These interests are characterized by a particular objective that emphasizes the subject matter of the person's decisions.

According to Sandstrom, a behavioral and quantitative theory or method for examining a complicated social phenomenon is provided by the optimal foraging theory. It puts ideas like objectives, currencies, other approaches, and particular tactics into practice within the framework of researchers' information-gathering and production. The theory also offers a means and a catalyst for developing and testing theories regarding the constraints of the environment and the decision-making of researchers.

Kuhlthou's Model:

Kuhlthau conducted research on how pupils look for information when writing: On the basis of this, she suggested a seven-stage model:

- task initiations
- topic selection
- pre-focus exploration
- focus formulation
- information collection
- search closure or presentation (writing).

Wilson remarks that in highlighting the emotions connected to the different phases and activities, Kuhlthau's model is more universal than Ellis's concept. Vakkaris suggests a task-based model that begins with a focus and is based on Kuhlthau's approach. According to Vakkari, the discovery of a focus—which is analogous to the research hypothesis—is essential to any search procedure.

Ingwersen's model:

From the standpoint of how people engage with IR systems. "...focuses on identifying processes of cognition which may occur in all the information processing elements involved," according to Ingwersen's cognitive paradigm.

Ingwersen's model is a little too straightforward. Upon closer inspection, this model bears a striking resemblance to existing models of information-seeking behavior. Specifically, Wilson's models' environmental factors and the user's cognitive space and social/organizational environment are similar, and the general orientation toward questions directed at an IR system suggests a problem with active search, which is the focus of the majority of information-seeking models.

However, Ingwersen clarifies several other aspects.

- First, he shows that the roles of the information user, document author, intermediary, interface, and IR system within each section of his model are the outcome of explicit or implicit cognitive models of the relevant domain at that specific moment. As a result, users have implicit models of their work tasks, information needs, problems, and goals.

- Second, Ingwersen introduces the IR system, arguing that it is essential to include the system that identifies the information objects that the inquirer may find interesting in a whole model of information-seeking behavior.
- Thirdly, he demonstrates how different cognitive changes occur when a user transitions from a life-world scenario where they encounter an issue or set a goal to one where they may effectively explore a collection of information objects and find helpful items.
- He concludes by highlighting the necessity of successfully communicating these models or cognitive structures and their modifications to the user, author, and IR system designer, who will all be a part of the "system."

Fig: Ingwersen's model diagram .

(Source - https://www2.hawaii.edu/~donnab/lis610/TDWilson_Only_1999.pdf)

(It is used for purpose of study)

Belkin's Model :

According to Belkin and his colleagues' ASK (Anomalous States of Knowledge) model, an information-seeking process starts with a problem, but at first, neither the problem nor the information required to address it are fully comprehended. As a result, the information system should facilitate interactive search processes, and information searchers must go through an iterative process to formulate a search request.

Belkin et al.'s episode model focuses on the steps taken during an information search, from scanning to searching, under the parameters of "resource considered," "mode of retrieval," and "goal of interaction." This model's premise is that individuals frequently search in a variety of ways during a series of information retrieval sessions.

The four dimensions of "scanning to searching," "goal of interaction," "mode of retrieval," and "resource considered" allow Belkin's model to characterize any one information-seeking approach based on where it falls.

Saracevic's Model:

The stratified model begins with the presumptions that

- (i) people utilize information by interacting with IR systems, and
- (ii) that information use is linked to cognition and situational applicability.

The Saracevic 1996 model was developed.

Users and computers are the main components of the stratified model; each has a variety of variables of its own and communicates through an interface. While the interface can effectively support or frustrate other interactions on its own, it is not the focus of interactions; rather, it instantiates a range of interactions. Interaction can be conceptualized as a series of events taking place on multiple interconnected levels or strata. Different components and/or particular procedures are involved at each stratum or level. On the human side, processes might be cognitive, psychological, or physiological (such as visual, tactile, or auditory). They could be both physical and symbolic on the computer side.

- The interface facilitates a surface-level interaction where:

Through an interface with a computer, users conduct a dialogue by uttering commands and receiving computer statements in response. This allows them to do more than just searching and matching, as shown in the traditional IR model. They can also do a variety of other tasks or "things," like understanding and eliciting information about the characteristics of a particular computer component or information resource; browsing; navigating within and among information resources, including distributed ones; figuring out the status of a process; visualizing displays and results; getting and giving different kinds of feedback; passing judgments; and so forth.

- With predetermined procedures and "understandings," computers engage in communication with users and supply predetermined answers; they may also elicit responses from the user or seek responses in return.

Fig: Saracevic's model diagram .

(Source - Saracevic, Tefko. (1997). The stratified model of information retrieval interaction:
Extension and applications.
(It is used for purpose of study)

Conclusion :

The information behavior models concentrate on the small-scale activities that users engage in on a daily basis within certain social and contextual situations that may have an impact on their information behavior. Ellis and Kuhlthau's models concentrate on the several steps that make up the information-seeking process.

The study of how people perceive and fill in cognitive gaps to make sense of their environment is made possible by Dervin's Sense-making method and process model. A study of consulting engineers' information behavior in their search for pertinent information that could aid in problem-solving would benefit greatly from a knowledge of the sense-making process.

The debate makes it clear that while each model represents a distinct approach to information-seeking behavior research, they also overlap or are comparable in certain ways. All of the models had the characteristic that using information is a multi-phase process.

These stages involve determining the information needs, deciding to utilize the information, choosing and obtaining information sources, locating and obtaining the information, processing and interpreting the information, and using the information.

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